

Intermolecular biocatalytic amide formation from aldehyde and amine using an engineered repurposed aldehyde dehydrogenase

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Amide formation represents a key reaction in the synthesis of pharmaceuticals for which environmentally friendly alternatives are sought after. In *Science*, Gao *et al.* report a biocatalytic oxidative strategy exploiting a redesigned aldehyde dehydrogenase that allows the coupling of aldehydes with amines at the expense of an oxidant [NAD(P)⁺, molecular oxygen].

The amide moiety is among the most commonly occurring functionalities in drug molecules, with over 40% of bioactive compounds containing an amide bond.¹ Owing to their high prevalence in pharmaceuticals, efficient and ideally environmentally benign methods for amide bond formation are in high demand.² Many of the established synthetic amidation approaches utilize carboxylic acids as starting materials requiring activation using stoichiometric amounts of coupling agents, which in turn results in unfavorable atom economies and substantial amounts of waste.

Employing biocatalysts to produce amides may potentially help to overcome the aforementioned challenges. Various enzymes have been described to catalyze amide bond formation reactions, usually starting from carboxylic acids, esters or nitriles.³⁻⁶ Furthermore, oxidative biocatalytic methods starting from e.g. primary alcohols instead of carboxylic acids were developed recently. For instance, galactose oxidase was used to transform amino alcohols to a cyclic imine intermediate which was oxidized further to the corresponding lactam with either xanthine oxidoreductase or aldehyde oxidase in one pot.⁷ Similarly, intramolecular oxidative lactamization was achieved starting from amino alcohols at the expense of molecular oxygen using horse liver alcohol dehydrogenase in combination with an NADPH oxidase.⁸ This year, intermolecular amide formation starting from alcohols and amines was reported at the expense of molecular oxygen using alcohol dehydrogenases (ADHs) and an NADPH oxidase.⁹ Although these publications have indicated that alternative oxidative biocatalytic routes for amide bond formation are feasible, their applicability is limited either to a narrow substrate scope (intramolecular amide formation starting from amino alcohols) or by the requirement for a high excess of the amine donor (100 equiv. in the case of ADH) probably to elevate the concentration of the spontaneously formed hemiaminal intermediate. Compared to the previous publications, Gao *et al.* present an elegant method for amide bond formation starting from aldehydes or alcohols applicable to a wide range of substrates and requiring approximately equimolar amounts of the amine donor.¹⁰

In the work of Gao *et al.*, aldehyde dehydrogenases (ALDHs) were repurposed for amide bond formation instead of carboxylic acid formation. This was achieved by avoiding hydrolysis of the reactive thioester intermediate and by promoting the attack of the amine substrate at this reactive species to obtain the amide (Figure 1A). In detail, the reaction mechanism involves a nucleophilic attack of a cysteine residue on the aldehyde leading to a tetrahedral thiohemiacetal intermediate. Subsequently, oxidation via hydride transfer to NAD(P)⁺ leads to the activated thioester. In the natural pathway this is followed by an attack of a water molecule

on the thioester intermediate, resulting in its hydrolysis and the release of the carboxylic acid. In their work, Gao *et al.* engineered the enzyme to accept an amine nucleophile over the water molecule to achieve aminolysis instead of hydrolysis. This rechanneling strategy exploiting the reactive thioester intermediate allows for amidation using stoichiometric amounts of the amine substrate.

As a first step in their work, a panel of ALDHs was screened for promiscuous activity towards oxidative amidation with ammonia. The aldehyde dehydrogenase PHBDD from *Pseudomonas putida* was selected as a promising candidate for further experiments due to detected trace activity for amide formation. The enzyme was then engineered to minimize the hydrolysis of the thioester intermediate in favor of aminolysis (Figure 1B). For this purpose, the conserved R166 and E259 residues were identified as crucial for the activation of water and hydrolysis of the thioester and were therefore mutated via site saturation mutagenesis. The variant R166M-E259L (M1), for which the two conserved hydrophilic residues were changed to hydrophobic ones, exhibited the highest oxidative amidation activity when ammonia was used as a nucleophile (>500-fold lower acid formation than the wild-type). Additionally, the variant was able to accept ethylamine, although in this case acid formation was predominant. Based on crystallographic data, eight more residues in the binding pocket were identified as potential interaction points with the thioester intermediate and exchanged. Substitution of residues L163 and T234 to small side chain residues like glycine, yielded the variant M1 L163G-T234G (M2) with increased conversion, higher amide selectivity and ability to accept bulkier amines. The mutation L163G enlarged the binding pocket and reduced steric hindrance, allowing the acceptance of alkylamines. Residue T234 was found to be a bottleneck in the amine access tunnel and its mutation to glycine expanded the tunnel space, contributing to improved selectivity for bulkier amines. Moreover, the residue P156 (not shown in Figure 1B) located close to T234 was identified as a potential hotspot for further mutagenesis. Through expansion of the library of variants, the authors were able to widen the substrate scope and achieve amidation activity also with anilines. The evolved variants showed a broad substrate scope for both aldehydes and amines.

A similar approach was applied to engineer five other ALDHs. Increasing the hydrophobicity of the enzyme binding pocket to prevent the activation of water resulted in increased oxidative amidation activity in each case. This suggested that this strategy represents a general principle for repurposing ALDHs for amide formation.

Finally, a one-pot cascade was developed to overcome issues related to the instability of the aldehyde substrates. To achieve this, alcohol substrates were oxidized by an alcohol dehydrogenase (ADH) to the corresponding aldehydes, which were then used for the oxidative amidation catalyzed by the evolved ALDH. To avoid the use of stoichiometric amounts of NADP⁺, a recycling system employing nicotinamide oxidase (NOX) as catalyst and molecular oxygen as oxidant was installed. The evolved ALDH was also tested for the synthesis of pharmaceutical active ingredients (API) on preparative scale. For this purpose, an *E. coli* whole-cell biocatalyst expressing ALDH and NOX was prepared and successfully implemented in gram-scale synthesis of different pharmaceutically relevant molecules, such as lazabemide and a precursor of vadadustat.

Through their work, Gao *et al.* were able to expand the repertoire of known biocatalytic routes towards amides. Comparing their developed method to other established biocatalytic amidation approaches, illustrates its potential advantages and challenges (Figure 1C). Most notably, the method allows for amidation using both aromatic and aliphatic substrates possessing various functionalities. Hydrolases such as lipases/esterases/proteases/acyltransferases show a broad substrate tolerance on the carboxylic acid side, while the amine spectrum is getting slowly extended. Selected ligases have been described for a broad substrate spectrum; these enzymes depend on ATP which

needs to be recycled to establish an efficient process. Nitrile hydratases can only be used to synthesize primary amides, whereas amidation with alcohol dehydrogenases has only been demonstrated with short chain aliphatic amines required in large excess. One of the potential challenges of using ALDHs is that, as opposed to i.e., hydrolases, they require NAD(P)⁺. To avoid the use of stoichiometric amounts of the cofactor, a recycling system was implemented at the expense of molecular oxygen using another enzyme (NOX).

Overall, repurposing ALDHs for amidation unlocks a new avenue of synthesizing amides starting from low-activation-state compounds, such as aldehydes and alcohols, thereby expanding the repertoire of possible precursors and providing a novel alternative to traditional amide synthesis methods.

Figure 1. Biocatalytic oxidative amidation catalyzed by engineered aldehyde dehydrogenases (ALDH) starting from aldehydes and amines and comparison with other methods. (A) Reaction mechanism of ALDH: after the formation of a thiohemiacetal intermediate and hydride transfer to NAD(P)⁺, the thioester intermediate can either undergo hydrolysis (natural pathway), yielding carboxylic acids or aminolysis generating amides (engineered amide pathway). (B)

Crystal structures of the binding pocket of the wild type (left panel, PDB: 9JW2) and the engineered ALDH able to efficiently catalyze amide formation (right panel, PDB: 9JVL). The residues subjected to mutagenesis are displayed as grey sticks, the nucleophilic Cys₂₉₃ is shown in magenta. The co-crystalized amide product is shown in cyan. (C) Comparison of different enzyme classes used for amide formation, with focus on reaction parameters such as substrates, required cofactors, additional enzymes needed for cofactor recycling or scavenging of by-products (H₂O₂), and reaction media.

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1. Ertl, P.; Altmann, E.; McKenna, J. M., 2020, **The Most Common Functional Groups in Bioactive Molecules and How Their Popularity Has Evolved over Time**. *J. Med. Chem.* 63, 8408-8418.
2. Bryan, M. C.; Dunn, P. J.; Entwistle, D.; Gallou, F.; Koenig, S. G.; Hayler, J. D.; Hickey, M. R.; Hughes, S.; Kopach, M. E.; Moine, G.; Richardson, P.; Roschangar, F.; Steven, A.; Weiberth, F. J., 2018, **Key Green Chemistry research areas from a pharmaceutical manufacturers' perspective revisited**. *Green Chem.* 20, 5082-5103.
3. Lubberink, M.; Finnigan, W.; Flitsch, S. L., 2023, **Biocatalytic amide bond formation**. *Green Chem.* 25, 2958-2970.
4. Winn, M.; Richardson, S. M.; Campopiano, D. J.; Micklefield, J., 2020, **Harnessing and engineering amide bond forming ligases for the synthesis of amides**. *Curr. Opin. Chem. Biol.* 55, 77-85.
5. Petchey, M. R.; Grogan, G., 2019, **Enzyme-Catalysed Synthesis of Secondary and Tertiary Amides**. *Adv. Synth. Catal.* 361, 3895-3914.
6. Kua, G. K. B.; Nguyen, G. K. T.; Li, Z., 2024, **Enzymatic Strategies for the Biosynthesis of N-Acyl Amino Acid Amides**. *ChemBioChem* 25, e202300672.
7. Herter, S.; McKenna, S. M.; Frazer, A. R.; Leimkühler, S.; Carnell, A. J.; Turner, N. J., 2015, **Galactose Oxidase Variants for the Oxidation of Amino Alcohols in Enzyme Cascade Synthesis**. *ChemCatChem* 7, 2313-2317.
8. Huang, L.; Sayoga, G. V.; Hollmann, F.; Kara, S., 2018, **Horse Liver Alcohol Dehydrogenase-Catalyzed Oxidative Lactamization of Amino Alcohols**. *ACS Catal.* 8, 8680-8684.
9. Damian, M.; Tseliou, V.; Peters, P.; Knaus, T.; Mutti, F. G., 2026, **Amide and Thioester Synthesis Via Oxidative Coupling of Alcohols with Amines or Thiols Using Alcohol Dehydrogenases**. *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.* 65, e202515469.
10. Gao, L.; Qiu, X.; Yang, J.; Hu, K.; Li, P.; Li, W.; Gao, F.; Gallou, F.; Kleinbeck, F.; Lei, X., 2026, **Engineered aldehyde dehydrogenases for amide bond formation**. *Science* 391, eadw3365.